

Tuberculosis Patients with Pregnancy and their Fetomaternal Outcome: An Analytical Study

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Abstract:

Background: During the research period, 4,300 patients gave birth; of these, 70 had TB diagnosis during the prenatal period, resulting in a 16.2 out of every 1,000 pregnant women have this condition. Anemia, intrauterine growth restriction, and premature birth were all significantly more common in TB patients. Our research revealed that the place, the severity of the illness, the gestation at diagnosis, and the TB complication all affect the mother and the results of pregnancy in TB-affected women.

Materials and Methods: A prospective monitoring study was done in a tertiary care center from March 2022 to March 2023, spanning one year. Our study looked at pregnant women between the ages of 20 and 45 who had been identified with tuberculosis during the fetal phase. This way, we could see how the disease affected both the mother and the baby. The study did not look at pregnant women who had tuberculosis (TB) in the past but were cleared after getting the right treatment. It also did not look at TB-positive women who did not give birth during the study time. Age, number of children, social position, date of diagnosis, and problems during pregnancy, childbirth, and the time after giving birth were all listed in each case file. In addition to the perinatal result, the kids' average birth weight, the number of preterm births, stillbirths, baby sadness, stays in the neonatal intensive care unit (NICU), and deaths as soon as they were born were all tracked.

Results: 4,300 patients gave birth Seventy of them received a tuberculosis (TB) diagnosis during the prenatal phase of the trial; this means that the prevalence rate per pregnant woman was 16.2/1,000. Among TB patients, anemia, intrauterine growth restriction, and preterm delivery were all markedly more prevalent. According to our research; a pregnant woman with tuberculosis may experience different perinatal outcomes depending on the location, severity of the illness, gestation at diagnosis, and TB complication.

Conclusion: At our facility, the rate of tuberculosis among expectant mothers was 16.2/1,000. It takes a strong suspicion to recognize the broad range of diseases and consequently the repercussions of tuberculosis (TB) in pregnant women, as well as to initiate treatment early for better outcomes.

Keywords: Tuberculosis, Maternal Tuberculosis, Tuberculosis Patients With Pregnancy, Fetomaternal Outcome.

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Introduction

Despite maternal tuberculosis (TB) being a relatively unknown and underappreciated illness, TB is nevertheless an important worldwide public health issue. Around 25% of individuals globally are thought to have been exposed to tuberculosis (TB), with 5–10% of those individuals ever developing active illness. [1] It is still unknown how common TB is among the Indian population, and it is most likely underestimated. [2] “This may be the result of vague clinical symptoms, inadequate diagnostic instruments for confirming

the illness, a lack of a standardized notification system, widespread disease exposure, a high prevalence of TB among the poor and undernourished population, and a lack of community understanding regarding the importance of seeking prompt and comprehensive treatment. [3] Although many reports are contradictory, several studies demonstrate that pregnant women and postpartum women in high-burden nations like India have a significantly increased risk of active tuberculosis infection. [4,5] The most prevalent site

of contamination is pulmonary TB, while extrapulmonary TB is becoming more and more common these days. Six Pregnancy-related physiological changes have been seen to frequently coincide with a variety of symptoms that patients come with, leading to a delayed diagnosis of tuberculosis. [6] Compared to women who are not pregnant, “During pregnancy, TB is not more common or hazardous. Women with tuberculosis have a twofold greater risk of preterm delivery or low birth weight, and a sixfold increased risk of neonatal death”. [7] Pregnancy-related tuberculosis has been linked to worse perinatal, fetal, and obstetric outcomes, according to several research. However, the largest barrier to the treatment of the illness is still early detection of tuberculosis. [8] This study aims to evaluate the chances of poor pregnancy outcomes in situations when the mother has TB.

Materials and Methods

Over the course of a year, from March 2022 to March 2023, a tertiary care facility conducted prospective observational research. To assess maternal and perinatal outcomes, “we included pregnant women in the age range of 20-45 years who were found to have tuberculosis during the prenatal period. After advising and obtaining consent those radiation dosages less than 0.01 mGy are safe during pregnancy, they were evaluated for symptoms, which included testing in their sputum and chest X-rays, especially in people who have pneumonic disease that is very far along in the disease process, for acid-fast bacillus. “Additionally, a multidisciplinary approach was employed, involving expert opinions in microbiology and pulmonary medicine. Women with history of tuberculosis who had received satisfactory treatment and were cured, as well as those who did not give birth during the research period, were omitted from the analysis. Information

gathered”. Age, gravida score, diagnosis date, and prenatal and postnatal problems were obtained from individual case data. Records were kept on the infants' mean birth weights, the prevalence of low for gestation, Apgar score, infant depression, and neonatal death hospitalization in the NICU, and stillbirths, in addition to the perinatal outcome.

Results

Prevalence Rate: A total of 4300 patients were included in our study, of which 70 had TB diagnosis during the antenatal period. This means that the prevalence rate in our study was 16.2 out of 1,000 expectant mothers, 52/70 (74.28%) and 18/70 (25.17%) of them had pulmonary tuberculosis had extrapulmonary TB.

Age

34 (48.6%) of the cases in our research, with a Aged 21.57 ± 4.22 years on average, are in the age category of 21–25 years.

Socioeconomic Status

32/70 (46%) of the pregnant women in our research had a moderate socioeconomic class, whereas 38/70 (54%) of the cases are from lower socioeconomic backgrounds.

Registrations Status

36/70 (51%) of the prenatal women in our research were registered, whereas 34/70 (49%) were not.

Distribution as per Site of TB

Figure 1 shows the site of the epidemic of TB. Of the 70 patients in this study, 18 (25.71%) were found to have extrapulmonary TB, which comprised intestinal TB (1.42%), TB meningitis (4.16%), abdominal TB (6%), tubercular lymphadenitis (13%), and Pott's spine (1.42%). Of the 70 patients, 52 (74.28%) were women with pulmonary TB.

Figure 1: Distribution according to the TB location

Antenatal Clinical Presentation: The prenatal women's clinical profile was displayed in Table 1. "The most common first symptom reported by 49/70 (70%) patients was a persistent cough with expectoration; fever followed Out of a total of 70 cases, 41 (58.57%) experienced additional

symptoms such as hemoptysis, tiredness, and dyspnea, whereas 24 (34.29%) had hemoptysis, fatigue, and dyspnea, and 10 (14.49%) reported weight loss.

A subset of people experienced atypical symptoms including cephalalgia, emesis, and cervical edema."

Table 1: Clinical profile of subjects

Symptoms	Seen in patients	Percentage
Fever	41	58.57
Additional symptoms include fatigue, hemoptysis, dyspnea, and loss of appetite.)	24	34.29
Loss of weight	10	14.29
Convulsions, vomiting, and headache	4	5.71
swollen neck	3	4.29
Experiencing abdominal pain and diarrhea.	3	4.29

Obstetrical Issues: Figure 1 "explains the TB-related problems. The most frequent obstetric problems linked to tuberculosis during pregnancy were intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR) (10%), anemia (15.71%), and premature labor (18.51%).

14 (20.28%) ladies. Fetal distress was the most prevalent reason for; 10 (14.49%) cesarean sections and 42 (60.86%) full-term normal deliveries.

A spontaneous abortion occurred in three.

Pregnancy Outcome: Figure 2 "illustrates the understanding of the result of the pregnancy. Preterm vaginal delivery occurred spontaneously in

At five months of pregnancy, one pregnant lady passed away from acute respiratory distress syndrome brought on by pulmonary tuberculosis".

Figure 2: problems during pregnancy for women with tuberculosis

Baby Weight Groups: Twenty babies were delivered weighing more than 2.5 kg, or a normal birth weight. In contrast, 35 out of 66 (63.02%) babies were born weighing less than 2.5 kg, and 11 (16.66%) babies were born weighing less than 1.5 kg, representing a very low birth weight.

Babies born to TB patients are admitted to the NICU: Figures 3 and 4 explain the newborn's admittance status to the intensive care unit. The leading cause of NICU admissions (38%) was preterm, Infants with a below-average weight upon birth,(31%), which came next.

Figure 3: The effects of TB on pregnancy

Figure 4: Neonatal outcome based on entrance to the NICU

Discussion

TB is a medical condition that is largely ignored, especially in India. In our investigation, the prevalence rate of TB is 1.62%. 52/70 (74.28%) of the study participants had pulmonary TB diagnoses, while 18/70 (25.17%) had extrapulmonary TB diagnoses. The indicator of average age in our group 23.57 ± 4.22 years old. Thirty-two women from moderate socioeconomic position and 38 from lower socioeconomic status participated in our study. Muniyandi's study found that those living in poverty had a greater frequency of tuberculosis. [9] Similar outcomes were seen in our investigation. Clinical indicators of aggressive tuberculosis in expecting moms can be worrisome,

and diagnosing the illness can occasionally be made more difficult by vague, nonspecific symptoms that are linked to the body's pregnancy-related reaction. [10] A persistent Expectoration together with a cough was the most prevalent presenting symptom in our research, occurring in 49 out of 70 patients (70%) and followed by fever in 41 out of 70 patients (58.57%) and weight loss in 10 out of 70 patients (14.49%). A few individuals also reported unusual symptoms as headache, vomiting, and swelling in the neck.

The intensity of the illness, the location of the TB infection, the patient's gestational age at diagnosis, HIV coinfection, medication, and treatment compliance are some of the variables that affect the

impact of tuberculosis (TB). Our research has demonstrated a higher frequency of premature labor, anemia, IUGR, oligohydramnios, and other prenatal problems. Early TB therapy, starting in the initial two trimesters of gestation, is preferable to a delayed diagnosis in the third trimester. Enhanced the mother's prognosis. Based on research by Sengupta et al. [11], "Loto and Awowole, [12] Mahendru et al. [13], our study's findings were consistent with extrapulmonary factors being linked to low birth weight, a low Apgar score, a greater frequency of preterm, intrauterine growth restriction, small for gestation," and an increased likelihood of newborn mortality.

"Pregnancy-related TB has to be identified and given a full course of anti-tubercular medication due to the significant danger that an active TB infection poses to expectant mothers and their fetuses." Breastfeeding is acceptable for TB patients who are on anti-tubercular medication. The effectiveness of current medication therapy is such that it is not advised for a mother and child to be separated. The perinatal morbidity of uninfected women and pregnant women using anti-tuberculous medications from the beginning of pregnancy was comparable. "We find that a high risk factor for unfavorable perinatal outcomes is tuberculosis. Pregnancy-related tuberculosis is a significant risk factor for poor newborn outcomes. In our research, we discovered revealed low birth weight was more common in pregnant TB patients, perinatal death, and NICU hospitalization.

In our investigation, the patient began exhibiting headache and convulsions at 5 months of gestation. Cerebrospinal fluid tests and brain computed tomography were used to confirm the diagnosis of tubercular meningitis. "After being sent to the intensive care unit, the patient's health worsened and she was unable to recover. Of the fifteen pregnant women in the current research who were diagnosed with TB in the first trimester, only two experienced stillbirths; of the twenty-three prenatal women who were, three neonatal fatalities and one maternal death were documented." Ten pregnant women were given a TB diagnosis during the third trimester; of these, two stillbirths and one neonatal fatality occurred. Early prenatal therapy for the condition lessens its detrimental effects on the perinatal outcome.

Conclusion and Recommendations

During the research period, our institute's prenatal ladies had a prevalence rate of 16.2 cases of tuberculosis per 1,000 pregnant women. our data indicates that Pregnancy with tuberculosis is linked to an increased risk of intrauterine growth restriction, anemia, and premature labor. We discovered that the location, the intensity of the illness, the pregnancy age at diagnosis, tuberculosis

complications, and the start of therapy all affect the outcomes for mothers and babies in pregnant women with tuberculosis. "Therefore, women in the reproductive age; range receiving treatment for tuberculosis should be strongly advised to use contraception. Maternal TB being undiagnosed is still a scourge." The largest obstacle to TB care in the prenatal period is early detection of maternal TB.

Therefore, must use a patient-centered approach when making diagnoses, providing therapy, and therapy Regarding tuberculosis during the perinatal period, healthcare providers should make use of already-existing resources like antenatal care programs, particularly in underfunded, high-burden regions like India. Perinatal tuberculosis may be fatal and is quite difficult to diagnose.

The best way to check for evidence of TB is to examine the placenta in newborns born to TB moms. To treat TB in pregnant women and improve outcomes, it is necessary to have a high degree of suspicion of the disease's variable spectrum and associated problems. Early therapy can also be started.

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